

KAUNAS UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

In Lithuania, the *Labour Code*¹ (2016) and the *Act on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men*² (last amended in 2017) are the key legislation regulating how universities and research organisations address the issues of gender-based violence (GBV) at work and in education. The amended *Act on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men* obliges higher education and research institutions to ensure equal rights for women and men and to undertake measures to stop any sexual harassment and protect students and staff in these institutions (2017, Art. 5 para. 5).

Universities have developed policies on antidiscrimination, equal opportunities, and diversity and have integrated gender as a category on which grounds discrimination, harassment, and sexual harassment is prohibited. Prevention and protection against sexual harassment are often the only types of action which the specific policies have been adopted. Some universities developed these policies after the Conference of University Rectors adopted in 2020 the Guidelines for the Prevention of Sexual Harassment and Investigation of Its Incidences (hereinafter the Guidelines).³ All universities have integrated the Recommendations on the Approval, Embedding, and Monitoring of Academic Ethics Codes by Research and Higher Education Institutions⁴ (hereinafter the Recommendations) approved by the Ombudsperson for Academic Ethics and Procedures. The Recommendations do not specifically mention GBV in universities, but they refer to integrity, justice, trust, equality, and responsibility as the main principles of academic ethics.

According to data from 2021, there are 11 public and four private universities in Lithuania. Six public and one private university have adopted policy documents on equal opportunities including gender equality and four public universities have adopted Gender Equality Plans (GEPs).

¹ Labour Code, No. XII-260 (2016, last amended 2021). <https://www.e-tar.lt/portal/lt/legalAct/f6d686707e7011e6b969d7ae07280e89>.

² Act on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men, No. XII-2767 (2016, last amended 2017). <https://e-seimas.lrs.lt/portal/legalAct/lt/TAD/d6ed8e50a74a11e68987e8320e9a5185>.

³ The Conference of Universities' Rectors (2020). Guidelines for the Prevention of Sexual Harassment and Investigation of Its Incidence. https://lurk.lt/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/Seksualinio-priekabiavimo-prevencijos-ir-atvej%C5%B3-nagrin%C4%97jimo-gair%C4%97s-2020m-be-nuorod%C5%B3_T.pdf.

⁴ Rekomendacijos mokslo ir studijų institucijų akademinės etikos kodeksų priėmimo, įgyvendinimo ir priežiūros rekomendacijos, V-16, (2015, last amendment 2020, V-38). <https://etikostarnyba.lt/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/V-38.pdf>

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

Kaunas University of Technology (KTU) adopted the Policy on Equal Opportunities and Diversity (hereinafter the Policy), which follows the requirement enshrined in the Labour Code to develop and implement policies on gender equality and equal opportunities (*Labour Code*, 2016). The Policy is a more general document on gender equality that also addresses discrimination, harassment, and sexual harassment based on the same definitions of these concepts as specified in the *Act on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men* (2017). The Policy was updated in April 2021 by including a separate chapter on preventing sexual harassment in the university. This chapter applies the same definition of and main provisions on sexual harassment and its prevention that are enshrined in the Guidelines for the Prevention of Sexual Harassment and Investigation of Its Incidences adopted by the Conference of University Rectors in 2020.

The Policy is based on a set of principles. One of the principles states that the university does not tolerate and prohibits any behaviour such as harassment, sexual harassment, psychological violence, bullying, stalking, or the misuse of power.

URL

› Policy on Equal Opportunities and Diversity: https://ktu.edu/wp-content/uploads/2016/08/Lygiu_galimybiu_ir_ivairoves_politika.pdf

Entry into force: The document was adopted on 7 December 2018 and updated on 16 April 2021.

TRAINING

The Policy on Equal Opportunities and Diversity includes one chapter about the dissemination of information and awareness raising in the university community. Training is mentioned among its listed measures.

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

None. Issues relating to the integration of GBV into the curriculum are not covered in any document or practice.

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: The policy defines the following **four** forms of gender-based violence: sexual violence, sexual harassment, gender-based harassment, and stalking.

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Economic and Financial Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Physical Violence | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Stalking |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Psychological Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Organisational Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Online Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Harassment | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Harassment | |

7Ps covered: The Policy covers the following **6Ps**: prevalence, prevention, protection, provision of services, partnerships, and policies.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

Target groups

The Policy addresses academic staff, non-academic staff and students.

Specific vulnerable groups

The Policy addresses international students and international staff.

Intersectionality addressed

No

Bystanders addressed: No.

Role of perpetrators addressed: No.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: No.

Monitoring: No.

Evaluation: No.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

Yes. The Policy sets out a step-by-step procedure for reporting and investigation. It is **one procedure for all**.

The policy defines: Who to contact, how to report, responsible persons or units, investigation, sanctions, and some other issues.

Who to contact: University employees and students who experience a violation of equal opportunities have the right to file a complaint with the Commission of Equal Opportunities. The complaint can be submitted to the automatic system (pranesk.ktu.edu) or by e-mail: pranesk@ktu.lt

Responsible persons/units: The Commission of Equal Opportunities established by an Order of the Rector⁵ is in charge of the investigation.

Investigation procedure: The Commission of Equal Opportunities will start an investigation into an anonymised complaint if the complaint provides the identity of the alleged perpetrator, the location and date of the alleged incident or case, and other factual evidence or descriptions. It should inform both sides (the victim and the alleged perpetrator) within three days of receiving a note or complaint. The Commission will collect evidence, meet to discuss the investigation progress, and take a decision. Hearings will be held with the victim, perpetrator, and witnesses and these hearings and all collected evidence are recorded in the protocols.

Investigation timeline: The complaint should be resolved within one month. The duration of the investigation may be increased under certain circumstances, such as in the case of holidays or unforeseen circumstances.

Sanctions: Sanctions are applied pursuant to the Labour Code and other university regulations (without reference to concrete sanctions). The document includes the possibility of appeal for both the victim and the perpetrator. The Rector of the university has the authority to apply disciplinary measures when the Commission provides a report on the investigated incident and recommended sanctions. If the Rector is the perpetrator, then disciplinary measures are issued by the University Council.

This document reflects the situation as of January 2022.

Acknowledgment: *this vignette has been created on the basis of the work carried out by national researcher Giedre Blazyte and Vilana Pilinkaite Sotirovic in 2021, as part of the deliverable report D5.1 Inventory of policies and measures to respond to GBV in European universities and research organisations (2022). Available here: https://zenodo.org/record/5939082#.YfvXE_jTW5c*

⁵ Kauno technologijos universitetas (2018). Lygių galimybių ir įvairovės politika, jos įgyvendinimo tvarkos aprašas, No. A-636, (2018, last amendment 2021, No. A-176).

